

EDUCATIONAL INTERVENTIONS FOR CHILDREN WITH AUTISM

Dr. N. Subramanian

Principal

S Veerasamy Chettiar College of Education, Tenkasi District

Abstract

Communication, social interaction, and repetitive habits are the core hallmarks of autism. Autism causes individuals to think, move, interact, and process sensory and cognitive information in distinctive, unusual ways. One comparison that is frequently used is that people with autism have a different neurological "operating system" than people without the disorder. Autistic deficits cluster into three groups namely Communication Deficits, Social deficits, and Physical deficits. Educational programmes for kids with autism involve a range of particular techniques. In-depth analyses of intervention techniques to improve social interaction, impart social skills, and lessen disruptive maladaptive behaviours have recently been published. This paper has some brief summaries of various educational interventions exclusively for children with autism.

Keywords: *Autism, Deficits, Interventions*

Introduction

A condition that is typically diagnosed in childhood. Communication, social interaction, and repetitive habits are the core hallmarks of autism. Autism causes individuals to think, move, interact, and process sensory and cognitive information in distinctive, unusual ways. One comparison that is frequently used is that people with autism have a different neurological "operating system" than people without the disorder. While living in a sense-overloading society that doesn't understand them and rarely makes accommodations for them puts autistic individuals at a disadvantage, it's possible that what hurts them the most is always being characterised by what they can't do rather than what they can do.

Skill Behaviours in Autism

Autistic deficits cluster into three groups:

- **Communication Deficits:** Communication deficits include the inability of people with autism to initiate and maintain proper conversation as well as the use of incorrect and repetitive words.
- **Social Deficits:** Social deficits appear as the propensity for social isolation, trouble maintaining eye contact, failure to form healthy peer connections, and seeming lack of empathy in people with autism.
- **Physical Deficits:** Physical deficits manifest as bizarre body posture and stereotypical, repeated actions.

Special Schools for Children with Autism

When it comes to providing education for students with special needs, special schools have been crucial. Schools that specialise in autism frequently use a therapy-based approach. Teachers frequently have special education backgrounds and experience working with autistic youngsters. The key benefit of this method is that the lessons and classroom are specifically designed to address the difficulties in educating kids with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). The drawbacks include a lack of engagement with typical peers and the potential for placing an excessive focus on social skills at the expense of pupils' intellectual development.

Inclusive Schools for Children with Autism

When he cited the UK Warnock Committee Report in 1997, Jangira brought the idea of inclusive education to India. Mani (2000), citing the ideas of the "dual teaching model" and the "multi-skilled teacher

plan," said that he had pioneered inclusive education in India in the 1980s. The Indian government has also taken steps to support inclusive schooling for kids with disabilities. It is thought that the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) is an important step in this regard. Currently, it appears that the government is assisting in the education of kids with autism by making a few well-placed strategic interventions in the classroom. For instance, the Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE) has changed the examination process in a number of ways through the passage of bylaws, which have been in effect since February 2009.

Educational Interventions

Educational programmes for kids with autism involve a range of particular techniques. In-depth analyses of intervention techniques to improve social interaction, impart social skills, and lessen disruptive maladaptive behaviours have recently been published. Below are some brief summaries of various techniques.

Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA): "Applied" means "practice", "Behavior analysis" may be read as "learning theory," Applied Behavior focuses on the ideas that describe how learning occurs. One such principle is the use of positive reinforcement. A behaviour is more likely to be repeated when it is accompanied by some kind of incentive. Through decades of research, the discipline of behaviour analysis has created a variety of methods for boosting beneficial behaviours and lowering those that might be harmful or hinder learning. It concentrates on what individuals say and do (behaviour) and employs experimental investigations of how the environment affects behaviour to generate methods for behaviour modification. ABA enables us to comprehend how individuals obtain reward for various behaviours and successfully "learn" the behaviours that result in reinforcers.

Functional Behavior Analysis: It is a crucial component of the behaviorally oriented approach to treating undesirable behaviours. Instead of focusing on skill development, FBA often aims to identify a suitable intervention for certain behavioural difficulties. The objective is to pinpoint the antecedent circumstances and reinforcing mechanisms that give rise to and sustain behavioural issues. The majority of problem behaviours have some sort of adaptive purpose and are reinforced by the outcomes, such as gaining (1) adult attention, (2) a desired object, activity, or sensation, or (3) eluding a demand or undesirable scenario. To increase the efficacy and efficiency of behavioural support interventions, functional assessment is a rigorous, empirically supported process of information gathering (O'Neill et al., 1996).

Discrete Trial Training (DTT): Discrete Trial Training (DTT) is a crucial component of the behaviorally oriented approach to treating undesirable behaviours. Instead of focusing on skill development, FBA often aims to identify a suitable intervention for certain behavioural difficulties. The objective is to pinpoint the antecedent circumstances and reinforcing mechanisms that give rise to and sustain behavioural issues. The majority of problem behaviours have some sort of adaptive purpose and are reinforced by the outcomes, such as gaining (1) adult attention, (2) a desired object, activity, or sensation, or (3) eluding a demand or undesirable scenario. To increase the efficacy and efficiency of behavioural support interventions, functional assessment is a rigorous, empirically supported process of information gathering (O'Neill et al., 1996).

Picture Exchange Communication System (PECS): It is a special bundle of interventions for augmentative and alternative communication for people with autism spectrum disorder and associated developmental difficulties. The programme aims to give nonverbal people a means of expressive communication. Line drawings are specifically utilised to represent commonplace items, cuisines, and activities, and the PECS procedure starts by developing straightforward requests. The instructor receives the picture of the item, meal, or activity from the learner, who subsequently receives what is shown in the picture. Carrier phrases, like "I want candy," are introduced when the learner improves at asking favoured

products. Basic behavioural concepts including shaping, differential reinforcement, and transfer of stimulus control are the foundation of the PECS system.

Pivotal Response Training (PRT): PRT aims to employ educational methods in crucial contexts that influence a wide range of target behaviours. When crucial areas are affected, other crucial development areas benefit significantly as a result. This incidental teaching method involves feedback, modelling, role-playing, and didactic instruction. Utilising the learner's interests, motivation, and requirements as the foundation for education, the teacher makes the most of naturally occurring chances. The two "pivotal" behaviours that are the cornerstones of PRT are motivation and the capacity to react to a variety of inputs. Because it causes simultaneous changes in other associated behaviours, motivation is a crucial behaviour (Koegel et al., 1987). Direct reinforcement that is tied directly to the behaviour being taught is known as reinforcement.

Facilitated Communication: It is an augmentative communication technique that allegedly enables people with communication and other difficulties to express themselves in ways that go far above what is thought to be their capacity limits. According to Jacobson, Mulick, and Schwartz (1995), the method entails supporting a nonverbal person's hand to make it simpler for them to type words on a typewriter, computer keyboard, or other communication device. These folks can type extraordinary FC increased thoughts and ideas with the help of hand-over-hand support or other sorts of physical assistance from a person without impairments. People with severe disabilities supposedly communicate that they have normal IQ and sophisticated social skills and knowledge with only a brief introduction to FC.

Structured Teaching: According to Mesibov, Shea, and Schopler (2005), structured teaching is a visually based method for developing highly structured environments that serve people with autism in a range of educational, social, and residential contexts. Instead of focusing on the child's weaknesses, the Treatment and Education of Autistic and Related Communication Handicapped Children (TEACCH) technique was created by Schopler, Mesibov, and Hearshey in 1995. Because of its developmental and behavioural foundations, TEACCH may be seen as an eclectic programme (Schopler & Mesibov, 1995). It is one of the methods of autism intervention that is most regularly used, and it is especially well-liked by special education programmes in public schools.

Developmental Models: The main focus of treatment for autism is developing social connections because it is a social disorder. This is accomplished through offering chances for play and social engagement at home, in a preschool that integrates with the community, and during one-on-one instruction. The target audience for the programme is kids between the ages of 2 and 5. The development of communication, play, sensory, and motor abilities is emphasised in the curriculum, which also encourages self-reliance and involvement in social activities. The Denver paradigm is a thorough "best practises" paradigm that lacks a specific theoretical foundation. The Denver approach, which is centred primarily on employing play, interpersonal interactions, and activities to build symbolic cognition and educate the capacity of communication, aims to address critical inadequacies in imitation, emotion sharing, theory of mind, and social perception. (Handleman & Harris, 2001.)

Multi Sensory Stimulation: Multi sensory stimulation is a therapeutic regime used for people with developmental disabilities, For those with developmental difficulties, dementia, and brain injuries, multisensory stimulation is a common therapy approach. To increase alertness and consciousness in the subject, this entails giving sensory stimulation across a variety of modalities (tactile, visual, aural, gustatory, olfactory, and proprioceptive). A range of sensory experiences can be enjoyed and controlled in multi-sensory environments. This intervention has recently become more widely employed and is applicable in all parts of life. A snoezelen room with equipment to stimulate different senses, such as using lighting effects,

music, sounds, and scents, is traditionally needed for this procedure. The tactile senses can be used to examine various materials on the wall and floor that have various textures.

Early and Intensive Behavioural Intervention (EIBI): It is typically described as comprehensive applied behaviour analytic programming that focuses on a variety of abilities that are important for early childhood development. According to the American Psychological Association's evaluation rubric for assessing the level of empirical support for interventions, only this method of intervention with young children with autism meets the strict requirements for qualification as a well-established and effective intervention. This classification calls for several controlled trials of the intervention in comparison to a variety of suitable controls, together with unmistakable proof of the target intervention's superiority (Chambliss & Hollon, 1998). In order to prepare children to learn from and succeed in typical home and school environments with the fewest supports possible, EIBI aims to increase intellectual (i.e., communication, cognitive, academic) skills and adaptive functioning (i.e., social skills, self-care skills, safety). It also aims to decrease the ASD symptoms and deficits.

Video Modeling: For its practical and successful use in the behavioural sciences, video modelling is a method that has been well-documented (Dowrick & Jesdale, 1991). In video modelling (VM), a subject watches videos of a model or models performing a behaviour, and then the subject is helped and encouraged to mimic the observed behaviour. Modelling techniques are based on Albert Bandura's (1977) theory of social learning, commonly known as observant learning. Due to the distinctive attractiveness of digital technology, video modelling is both easily available and inexpensive. There are many justifications put up in favour of using video modelling with autistic children. Videos can easily be tailored to children's requirements and can include a variety of social contexts and settings to help with behaviour acquisition, maintenance, and generalisation. Videos may also include vicarious reinforcing stimuli that are contingent on the desired behaviours. Children with ASD frequently have overly selective attention or a small field of focus (Charlop-Christy & Daneshvar, 2002; Buchsbaum et al., 1992). By concentrating their attention on the key cues, people with autism seem to be able to pay attention better thanks to video modelling.

Conclusion

Children with autism suffer with their inability to express their needs and have little social connection, among other things. Additionally, physiological symptoms like impaired motor skills, issues with eating and digestion, and sleep issues make them worse. These difficulties frequently take the form of numerous maladaptive behaviours, which further restrict their ability to interact socially with their peers. Children with autism spectrum disorders (ASD) have difficulty understanding and interacting with their surroundings. The educational interventions may have an impact and result in long-lasting, favourable changes in the child. Additionally, it aids in the development of abilities in autistic children that can enhance their quality of life. Even though intervention can be advantageous at any age, early intervention is crucial because learning new skills is much simpler when you're very young. This is because our brains go through important developmental stages in early childhood, and taking advantage of these stages can make learning new things simpler.

References

1. Hewitson, Jessie. (2018). *Autism: How to raise a happy autistic child*. New York: Orion Publishing Group.
2. Myers, S.M., Johnson, C.P., & Council on Children with Disabilities. (2007). Management of Children With Autism Spectrum Disorders. *Pediatrics*, 120, 5, 1162 -1182. doi: 10.1542/peds.2007-2362.
3. Fowler, S. (1997). *Sensory Stimulation*. Victoria: Coa press.

4. Fisher, A. G., Murray, E. A., & Bundy, A. C. (1991). *Sensory integration: Theory and practice*. Philadelphia: F.A. Davis.
5. Handleman, J.S., & Harris, S.L.(2001). *Preschool education programs for children with autism*. Austin, Texas: PRO-ED.
6. Schopler, E., Reichler, R.J., & Renner, B.R. (1988). *The childhood Autism rating scale (CARS)*. Los Angeles: Westem Psychiatric Services.
7. Mesibov, G., Shea, V., & Schopler, E. (2005). *The TEACCH approach to autism spectrum disorders*. New York: Kluwer Academic/Plenum Publishers.
8. Calculator, S. (1992). *Facilitated communication: Calculator responds*. American Journal of Speech-Language Pathology, 1,23-24.
9. Jacobson, J.W., Mulick, J.A., & Schwartz, A.A.(1995). A history of facilitated communication: Science, pseudoscience, and anti science. *American Psychologist*, 50, 750-765.
10. Koegel, R.L. & Egel, A.L. (1979). Motivating autistic children. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 88(4), 418-426. doi: 10.1037/0021-843X.88.4.418 Koegel, R.L., Schreibman, L., Good, A., Cemiglia, L., Murphy, C, & Koegel, L.K. (1987). *How to teach pivotal behaviors to children with autism: A training manual*. Santa Barbara, CA: University of California.
11. Frost, L., & Bondy, A. (1994). *The Picture Exchange Communication System training manual*. Cherry Hill, NJ: Pyramid Educational Consultants, Inc.
12. Smith, B.A. (2012). *Sensory Stimulation Activities for Autism*. Retrieved April 25, 2012, fi-om <http://www.apastyle.org/learn/faqs/web-page-no-author.aspx>.
13. Smith, E.E. (1999). Jonides. *The Journal of Science*, 283, 1657-1661.
14. O'Neill, R. E., Homer, R. W., Albin, R. W., Sprague, J. R., Storey, K., & Newton, J. S. (1997). *Functional assessment and program development for problem behavior: A practical handbook* (2nd ed.). Pacific Grove, A: Brooks/Cole.
15. Chambless, D. L., & Hollon, S. D. (1998). Defining empirically supported therapies. *Journal of Consulting & Clinical Psychology*, 66, 7–18.
16. McEachin J. J., Smith T. & Lovaas O. I. (1993). Long-term outcome for children with autism who received early intensive behavioral treatment. *American Journal on Mental Retardation*, 97 (4), 359–372.